

Multiple Quantum Dot Tunneling in a Semiconductor and Its Wave Function and Probability Density[†]

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Abstract—Light Emitting Diodes (LEDs) are semiconductor devices that emit light with a narrow spectral distribution when an electric current is applied. Wavelength of light emitted by the LEDs is a direct result of the band gap of the emissive layer comprising the quantum dot which in turn, related to the semiconductor composition. Quantum dots (also known as semiconductor nanocrystals) can be used as down converters applied onto short wavelength LED chips and used to generate visible and infrared light these quantum dots are synthetic crystals and are so small that sometimes it is referred as “artificial atom” and their optical and electronic properties differ from small to large quantum dots. Their electronic properties determined by their size and color. Bigger quantum dots emit wavelength like red and smaller quantum dot emit wavelength like green. This paper discloses tunneling through barrier using quantum dot into a semiconductor with single, double and triple barriers. If barrier is too high quantum dot is repelled back and quantum dot tunneling cannot be performed. Quantum dot tunneling wave function and probability density for constant, step, single barrier and double barriers are also plotted and numerical results are documented.

Keywords—Quantum mechanics; Quantum dots; semiconductor; artificial atom; Quantum dot tunneling; Light Emitting Diode (LED); Organic Light Emitting Diode (OLED)

I. INTRODUCTION

A Quantum dot is a tiny fragment of matter that is so small that it's packed into a solitary point (in other words, it's zero-dimensional). As a result, the particles inside it that carry electricity (electrons and holes, which are places that are missing electrons) are constrained and have well defined energy levels as per the laws of quantum theory a bit like individual atoms (atoms). Quantum dots are crystals a few nanometers wide, so they're typically a few dozen atoms across and contain anything from maybe a hundred to a few thousand atoms. They are made from a semiconductor such as silicon (a material that's neither a conductor nor an insulator, but can be chemically treated so it works like either). And although they are crystals, they act more like individual atoms therefore the name artificial atoms.

Quantum dots can be controlled to do useful things. For an example if you provide an atom energy, you can "energize" it: you can surge an electron inside it to a higher energy level. When the electron returns to a lower level, the atom discharges a photon of light with the equal energy that the atom originally consumed. The color (wavelength and frequency) of light an atom discharges depends on what the atom is; iron appears to be green when you excite its atoms by holding them in a hot conflagration, while sodium appears to be yellow, and that's because of the way their energy levels are organized. The rule is that several different atoms discharge

different colors of light. All this is more likely because the energy levels in an atoms have set values; in other words, they are quantized [1], [2]. Double quantum barriers are the one of the simplest semiconductor hetero structures demonstrating tunnel coupling [3]. Distinguishing with recent tunneling spectroscopy experiments shows promise and allows an unambiguous rendezvous of the conductance peaks [4].

Figure 1. Illustrates that Quantum dot size and color (Image Credit Ref. [2])

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II. QUANTUM DOT TUNNELING

Quantum dot tunneling is similar to tunneling in the ordinary diode except that here quantum dot is used. Since quantum dot is very tiny and nano size. A simulation is performed to understand quantum dot tunneling for high barrier, single, double and triple barrier low barrier with a light packet [6], [7].

III. QUANTUM DOT TUNNELING WITH HIGH BARRIER

A. Simulations

A simulation was performed for quantum dot with packet of light for tunneling through high barrier and quantum dot was repelled back [8].

Figure 2. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) with light patch and having high barrier

Figure 3. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) with light patch, having high barrier and specifying direction of movement (green color) for the quantum dot

Figure 4. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) with packet of light, moving across the high barrier

Figure 5. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) movement and changes in the packet of light due to barrier

Figure 6. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) movement and also shows high peak of light have occurred due to high barrier

Figure 7. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) has repelled back and heading back ward due to high barrier

Figure 8. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) has repelled back and heading back ward and also shows the low peak of light

Figure 9. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) has repelled back, heading back ward and also shows last remnants of packet of light for after the barrier

Figure 10. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) has repelled back, heading back ward and also shows last remnants of packet of light for before the barrier

B. Explanations of Graphs

Figure 2 explains setup for quantum dot (blue color) and high barrier. In Figure 3, the green arrow shows the angle of the quantum dot moving towards the barrier. Here recorded angle is 180.31. In Figure 4, that quantum dot is moving across the barrier with the recorded precision value of 1 with a light packet and speed of 6.50. In Figure 5, quantum dot is moving with the light packet slowly diminishing. In Figure 6 and 7 although light packet has made high peak value but because of the very high barrier quantum dot is repelled. In Figure 8 and 9 quantum dot is moving away. Figure 10 depicts last remnants of light packet.

C. Observations

- Quantum dot was not able to pass through the barrier because barrier was too high for a quantum dot to pass thorough
- High peak of light packet was noted caused due to high barrier
- Low peak of light packet was noted
- Last remnants of light packet for after and before barrier is noted
- Study of quantum dot with packet of light has been performed

IV. QUANTUM DOT TUNNELING WITH SINGLE LOW BARRIER

A. Simulations

A simulation was performed for quantum dot with packet of light for tunneling through single and low barrier and quantum dot was able to get the other side of the barrier.

Figure 11. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) on a two dimensional plane with light patch.

Figure 12. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) on a two dimensional plane with light patch and having single and small barrier

Figure 13. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) with light patch, having single barrier and specifying direction of movement (green color) for the quantum dot

Figure 14. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) with packet of light, moving across the single barrier

Figure 15. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) movement and also shows peak of light has occurred due to the barrier

Figure 16. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) and also shows high peak of light has occurred due to the barrier

Figure 17. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) has successfully passed through the single barrier with the light packet

Figure 18. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) remnants of packet of light

Figure 19. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) last remnants of packet of light

B. Explanations of Graphs

Figure 11 explains setup for quantum dot (blue color) and single low barrier. In Figure 13, the green arrow shows the angle of the quantum dot moving towards the barrier. Here recorded angle is 180.94. In Figure 14, that quantum dot is moving across the barrier with the recorded precision value of 1 with a light packet and speed of 4.42. In Figure 15, quantum dot is moving with the light packet slowly diminishing. In Figure 16 light packet had made a peak value. Figure 17 shows quantum dot has successfully cleared the barrier. In Figure 18 and 19 depicts last remnants of light packet.

C. Observations

- Quantum dot was successfully passed through the single low barrier
- High peak of light packet was noted caused due to barrier
- Low peak of light packet was noted.
- Remnants and last remnants of light packet for after and before barrier is noted

V. QUANTUM DOT TUNNELING WITH DOUBLE LOW BARRIER

A. Simulations

A simulation was performed for quantum dot with packet of light for tunneling through double and low barrier and quantum dot was able to get the other side of the barrier.

Figure 20. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) on a two dimensional plane with light patch and having double and small barrier

Figure 21. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) with light patch, having double barrier and specifying direction of movement (green color) for the quantum dot

Figure 22. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) with packet of light, moving across the double barrier

Figure 23. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) movement and also shows peak of light has occurred due to the barrier

Figure 24. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) has successfully passed through the first double barrier with the light packet

Figure 25. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) has successfully passed through the second double barrier with the light packet

Figure 26. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) last remnants of packet of light

B. Explanations of Graphs

Figure 20 explains setup for quantum dot (blue color) and double low barrier. In Figure 21, the green arrow shows the angle of the quantum dot moving towards the barrier. Here recorded angle is 180.15. In Figure 22, that quantum dot is moving across the barrier with the recorded precision value of 1 with a light packet and speed of 5.85. In Figure 23, quantum dot is moving with the light packet slowly diminishing. In Figure 24 quantum dot has successfully cleared first barrier. Figure 25 quantum dot has successfully cleared the second barrier. In Figure 26 depicts last remnants of light packet after and before the barriers

C. Observations

- Quantum dot was successfully passed through the double low barriers
- Peak of light packet caused due to barriers was noted
- Low peak of light packet was noted
- Last remnants of light packet for after and before barrier is noted

VI. QUANTUM DOT TUNNELING WITH TRIPLE LOW BARRIER

A. Simulations

A simulation was performed for quantum dot with packet of light for tunneling through triple and low barrier and quantum dot was able to get the other side of the three barriers.

Figure 27. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) on a two dimensional plane with light patch and having triple and small barrier

Figure 28. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) with light patch, having triple barrier and specifying direction of movement (green color) for the quantum dot

Figure 29. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) with packet of light, moving across the triple barrier

Figure 30. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) movement and also shows peak of light has occurred due to the barrier

Figure 31. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) has successfully passed through the first triple barrier with the light packet

Figure 32. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) has successfully passed through the second triple barrier with the light packet

Figure 33. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) has successfully passed through the third triple barrier with the light packet

Figure 34. Illustrates Quantum dot (blue color) last remnants of packet of light

B. Explanations of Graphs

Figure 27 explains setup for quantum dot (blue color) and triple low barrier. In Figure 28, the green arrow shows the angle of the quantum dot moving towards the barrier. Here recorded angle is 179.63. In Figure 29, that quantum dot is moving across the barrier with the recorded precision value of 1 with a light packet and speed of 6.50. In Figure 30, quantum dot is moving with the light packet slowly diminishing. In Figure 31 quantum dot has successfully cleared first barrier. Figure 32 quantum dot has successfully cleared the second barrier. In Figure 33 quantum dot has successfully cleared the second barrier. In Figure 34 depicts last remnants of light packet after and before the barriers

C. Observations

- Quantum dot was successfully passed through the triple low barriers
- Peak of light packet caused due to barriers was noted
- Low peak of light packet was noted
- Last remnants of light packet for after and before barrier is noted

TABLE I
SIMULATION NOTES FOR MULTIPLE QUANTUM DOT TUNNELING

Sl No	Simulation Specifications	High Quantum Barrier	Single Quantum Barrier	Double Quantum Barrier	Triple Quantum Barrier
1	Center (X-axis)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2	Center (X-axis)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
3	Precision	1	1	1	1
4	Speed	6.50	4.42	5.85	6.50
5	Angle	180.31	180.94	180.15	179.63
6	Sensitivity	max	max	max	max
7	Speedup	lowest	lowest	lowest	lowest

VII. QUANTUM DOT TUNNELING WAVE FUNCTION AND PROBABILITY

A different tool was used to describe quantum dot tunneling wave function and probability density. Graphs are plotted for different potentials for constant, step, single barrier and double barrier potential.

X-Axis for the wave function and probability density is position (nm) [Ref 4]

A. Wave Function and Probability Density for Constant Potential

Figure 35. Illustrates Quantum measurement for constant potential for 0 second (clk)

Figure 36. Illustrates Quantum measurement for constant potential for 4 seconds (clk)

Figure 37. Illustrates Quantum measurement for constant potential for 10.1 seconds (clk)

Figure 38. Illustrates Quantum measurement for constant potential for 13.2 seconds (clk)

Figure 39. Illustrates Quantum measurement for constant potential for 23.1 seconds (clk)

B. Explanation of Graphs

Wave functions and probability density for constant potential has been plotted from Fig 35 to 38. It depicts

Quantum measurement for Energy (eV), Wave Function and probability for 0, 4, 10.1, 13.2 and 32.1 seconds respectively.

C. Wave Function and Probability Density for Step Potential

Figure 40. Illustrates Quantum measurement for step potential for 0 second (clk)

Figure 41. Illustrates Quantum measurement for step potential for 3 seconds (clk)

Figure 42. Illustrates Quantum measurement for step potential for 12.5 seconds (clk)

Figure 43. Illustrates Quantum measurement for step potential for 17.6 seconds (clk)

D. Explanation of Graphs

Wave functions and probability density for step potential has been plotted from Fig 40 to 43. It depicts Quantum measurement for Energy (eV), Wave Function and probability for 0, 3, 12.5 and 17.6 seconds respectively.

TABLE II

SIMULATION NOTES FOR WAVE FUNCTION AND PROBABILITY DENSITY

Sl No	Wave Packet Properties	Constant potential	Step Potential
1	Initial Width	0.5	0.5
2	Initial Position	-2.0nm	-2.0nm
3	Average total energy	0.80eV	0.80eV
4	Potential Energy (V_1)	0.00eV	0.00eV
5	Potential Energy (V_2)	-	0.50eV
6	Step Position	-	0.0nm

E. Wave Function and Probability Density for Single Barrier Potential

Figure 44. Illustrates Quantum measurement for barrier/well potential for 0 second (clk)

Figure 45. Illustrates Quantum measurement for barrier/well potential for 3.2 seconds (clk)

Figure 48. Illustrates Quantum measurement for barrier/well potential for 16.7 seconds (clk)

Figure 46. Illustrates Quantum measurement for barrier/well potential for 7.8 seconds (clk)

Figure 47. Illustrates Quantum measurement for barrier/well potential for 11.0 seconds (clk)

F. Explanation of Graphs

Wave functions and probability density for single barrier potential has been plotted from Fig 44 to 48. It depicts Quantum measurement for Energy (eV), Wave Function and probability for 0, 3.2, 7.8, 11.0 and 16.7 seconds respectively.

G. Wave Function and Probability Density for Double Barrier Potential

Figure 49. Illustrates Quantum measurement for double barrier/well potential for 0 seconds (clk)

Figure 50. Illustrates Quantum measurement for double barrier/well potential for 3.5 seconds (clk)

Figure 53. Illustrates Quantum measurement for double barrier/well potential for 16.3 seconds (clk)

Figure 51. Illustrates Quantum measurement for double barrier/well potential for 6.1 seconds (clk)

Figure 52. Illustrates Quantum measurement for double barrier/well potential for 11.0 seconds (clk)

H. Explanation of Graphs

Wave functions and probability density for double barrier potential has been plotted from Fig 49 to 53. It depicts Quantum measurement for Energy (eV), Wave Function and probability for 0, 3.5, 76.1, 11.0 and 16.3 seconds respectively.

TABLE III

WAVE FUNCTION AND PROBABILITY DENSITY FOR SINGLE AND DOUBLE BARRIERS

Sl No:	Wave Packet Properties	Single Quantum Barrier	Double Quantum Barrier
1	Initial Width	0.5	0.5nm
2	Initial Position	-2.0nm	-20.0nm
3	Average Total Energy	0.80eV	0.80eV
4	Potential Energy (V1)	0.00eV	0.00eV
5	Potential Energy (V2)	0.50eV	0.50eV
6	Potential Energy (V3)	0.00eV	0.00eV
7	Potential Energy (V4)	-	0.50eV
8	Potential Energy (V5)	-	0.00eV
9	Barrier Edge (B1)	0.0nm	0.00nm
10	Barrier Edge (B2)	-	2.0nm
11	Barrier Width (BW1)	1.0nm	1.0nm
12	Barrier Width (BW2)	-	1.0nm

VIII. ADVANTAGES OF MULTIPLE QUANTUM TUNNELING

The tunneling effects are described on the bases of wave functions and probability density where ground state patterns undergoes non-trivial quantum transitions; at transitional values a new phase that is observable in addition of magnetization changes [8].

IX. RESULTS

What is claimed in this are

- Successfully performed quantum dot tunneling for single, double and triple low barriers.
- Peaks of light packet while tunneling has been noted.
- Remnants and last remnants of light packet has been noted.
- Performed quantum tunneling for high barrier and quantum dot was repelled back.
- Study of quantum tunneling in semiconductor has been performed.
- Quantum measurement for wave function and probability density has been plotted for constant, step, single barrier/well, double barrier/well voltages.

X. CONCLUSION

Quantum dot tunneling is very important phenomenon to understand properties in nanoscale for example in Scanning Tunneling Microscopy (STM). In this case multiple tunneling is performed to understand its complexity.

In this case multiple quantum dot tunneling has performed for large barrier which quantum dot was repelled back and for single, double and triple low barriers; quantum dot was successfully cleared with a light packet.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interest from author's point of view.

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